

ORIGINALRESEARCH

Assessment of Covid-19 Obsession Among Hospital Workers in Jos-South LGA Plateau State Nigeria

Dauda Akwai Saleh¹, Sherdung Palangshak¹

¹Department of Psychology Plateau State University Bokkos, Nigeria

Correspondence

Dauda Akwai Saleh
Corresponding Author:
salehakwai@plasu.edu.ng

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Abstract

The research assess COVID-19 obsession among hospital workers in Jos-South local government area of Plateau State Nigeria. A total of 162 hospital workers (82, 50.6% males and 80, 49.4% females) with mean age of 34.01 participated in this survey research. Four hypotheses were tested utilizing Chi-square at p = 0.05 level of significance, result revealed that older hospital workers had higher prevalence of COVID-19 obsession compared to younger hospital worker, $\chi^2 = 6.139$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.013$ ($p < 0.05$). The prevalence of COVID-19 obsession did not differ among hospital workers in terms of gender, $\chi^2 = 0.009$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.924$ ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, results revealed that hospital workers with tertiary education had higher prevalence of COVID-19 obsession compared to those with lower educational status, $\chi^2 = 7.168$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.028$ ($p < 0.05$). Finally, prevalence of COVID-19 obsession did not differ among hospital workers in terms of marital status, $\chi^2 = 6.996$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.072$ (> 0.050). The authors concluded that more attention should be given to hospital workers in terms of policy formulation being that they are at the forefront in the fight against COVID-19. Also, there is need for setting up of psychological service centres across hospitals in Nigeria which would go a long way in not just evaluating the mental health status of hospital workers in relation to COVID-19 but it will be beneficial to the general public in assessing psychology services easily.

Keywords: Covid-19; Obsession; Hospital Workers; Prevalence

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1. Introduction

Corona virus (COVID-19) is a pandemic that has affected the whole world, health workers are more exposed to the danger of being infected with the virus. Globally, health workers are working round the clock on finding a lasting solution to COVID-19. Due to the nature of the virus and adherence to COVID-19 protocol, people are becoming obsessed due to the virus. The virus, COVID-19 was reported in Wuhan, China, at the end of 2019 (Lu, Stratton, & Tang, 2020). The mental health status of individuals should be taken into consideration during and after the COVID-19 pandemic (Saleh, Arobo, Abel, Ibrahim, Damilep, Dakama & Terry, 2020). The manner at which an individual can be infected with COVID-19 is enough reason for people to be scared of the virus. The spread of COVID-19 has lead to frequent hand washing in line with COVID-19 safety protocol. Thus, the researchers in this study are interested in assessing COVID-19 obsession among health workers, with emphasis on understanding the

prevalence of COVID-19 obsession among health workers in relation to age, gender, educational status and marital status. Benatti, Albert, Maina, Fiorillo, Celebre and Nicolaia (2020) reported obsessions and compulsions relating to COVID-19 to include frequent internet checking, avoidance behaviours, work difficulties and sleep disturbances. Among health workers in a South-Eastern Nigerian state, Mbachu, Azubuike, Mbachu, Ndukwu, Ezeuko, Udigwe, Nnamani, Umeh, Ezeagwuna, Onah, Eze, Okereke, and Orji-Ifeanyi, (2020) reported that fear of death and lack of personal protective equipment had strong impact on healthcare workers attitude, with female healthcare workers having poor attitude to work than their male counterparts. According to Lu, et al (2020), the growing number of cases, deaths and fear in relation to COVID-19 have spread around the world as COVID-19 continues to dominate the world’s attention. Coronavirus disease 2019 has significant morbidity and mortality (Alhousseini, Sajid, Altayeb, Alyousof, Alsheikh, Alqahtani & Alsomali, 2021). According to Jelinek, Moritz,